

The Archival Opacity of Platforms Policies

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Paper presented at *4S – 2021 Meeting of the Society for the Social Studies of Science. Toronto / Online.*

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6425555

September 2021.

Introduction

The rules established by social media platforms to govern their relationship with billions of users are among the most important private policies in the world. Yet, not much has been written on how these policies changed over time, an aspect that seems essential to understand the historical transformation of these platforms into dominant spaces of global communication. In this paper, we discuss some initial findings of a project that aims to map out the end-users policies¹ of five mainstream platforms (Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, Instagram and Sound Cloud), with an emphasis on rules regulating copyright. In particular, the paper debates some methodological difficulties involved in the historical research of these rules, and presents the blueprint of an open repository of platforms policies that aims to partially circumvent these difficulties.

The first part of the paper argues that platforms policies appear to be concealed by a hardly discussed form of platform opacity, which we term *archival opacity*. By that we mean that platforms rules are not only presented in an intricate language (as it has been extensively argued elsewhere) but are also hidden from view by the way they are and are not archived in the platforms websites. The second part of the paper proposes that this sort of archival opacity calls for a public, transparent and independently built online repository, which we are currently developing – called the Platform Governance Archives. More than simply presenting the repository, the paper aims to generate critical and constructive feedback on the initiative.

1. The Archival Opacity of Platforms Polices: Fragmentation, Erasure and Flaws

Social media platforms, and the corporate conglomerates which govern them, are notoriously opaque (Pasquale, 2015). Despite growing social and political pressures, they have fiercely resisted independent analysis of their datafication systems – i.e., the way in which they incessantly produce data about their users so as to feed machine learning systems which will made decision about these same users. The exact directives and dynamics of human content moderation are often unknown (Wong & Solon, 2018). Employees are commonly bound by strict non-disclose agreements (Roberts, 2019).

One of the few easily accessible sources of information about how platforms work are their *policies*, defined here as the public texts, videos and graphs in which platforms lay down the formal rules governing the relationship between them and their various kinds of users (from ordinary people to advertisers). Such publicity is a legal obligation *and* a regulatory tool – if users are to follow platforms rules, they must of course know these rules in the first place.

This is not to say that these policies are themselves particularly clear. Years of research on e.g., Terms of Service and Privacy Agreements have shown convincingly that users rarely read these documents before signing them, and that this is at least partially due to these documents' format: long, confusing and written in overly technical legal language (see a recent discussion in Taber, May, Yahn-Krafft & Whittaker, 2020). This section discusses a different, rarely studied dimension of these policies' opacity – one that is related to how they are organized and recorded (or not) by companies.

Such *archival opacity* hinders access to both existing and previous versions of policies. First, there is the problem of *fragmentation*: current rules are not restricted to those of documents such as Terms of Service, Privacy Agreements and Community Guidelines. In fact, over time, they have become dispersed into sometimes dozens of URLs and buried in various Help pages that are not easily found. Second, there is plain *erasure*: few platforms have clearly organised archives of past policies, which

¹ Thus, policies regulating other sorts of users, such as advertisers, are not considered here.

were deleted from their webpages. Finally, we argue that some archives appear to be marked by various *flaws* – they are incomplete.

1.1. Fragmentation

When researchers, policymakers and journalists talk about “platforms policies”, they usually mean three kinds of documents (see e.g. Gillespie, 2018): Terms of Service (sometimes named Terms of Use) work as a sort of general contract between users and platforms; Privacy Agreement (alternatively called Privacy Policy and lately Data Policy) describe how platforms monitor their users, and how the data produced from this monitoring is used; and Community Guidelines (also named e.g., Community Standards) tell users what behaviours is un/acceptable in the platform. Even when we focus on only these kinds of documents, some level of temporal complexification can be noted. Two of the analysed platforms (Facebook, YouTube) had only Terms of Service and Privacy Policies when they went online; Community Guidelines were introduced later. The others (Twitter, Instagram and SoundCloud) began with only the Terms of Service in place, introducing their Privacy Policy and Community Guidelines months or even years later.

Yet, it is the use of a vast web of Help pages what makes the fragmentation platforms policies clearer. The relations between Help pages and policies have not been studied by platform governance scholars, who might assume that these pages merely organize, in a friendlier way, norms that can be found somewhere else in the platform’s website. However, as it became clear during our work, these spaces play a central role in platforms attempt to communicate how they function and what is expected from their users. For, in explaining some of the provisions presented in those more general documents (e.g., “The platform does not tolerate copyright infringement”), they also introduce new rules, as we explain next.

Due to space limitations, let us focus here on YouTube’s copyright Help pages to exemplify our argument. The first record we could find of this area of the platform is from May 2006. Named “Copyright tips”, it initially contained only one subpage, explaining the platform’s DMCA (Digital Millennium Copyright Act) policy. After 13 years of increasing complexification, by mid-2020, the same page, then named “Copyright on YouTube”, had two main subsections (“Learn about copyright” and “Support and troubleshooting”), each one composed of six pages. In these pages, the users would find information on e.g., how YouTube define a “copyright strike”, how their copyright content moderation algorithmic system works, how to dispute a decision by this system. Since these explanations could not be found in the Terms of Service and the Community Guidelines, this set of Help pages comprised arguably the most important copyright policy document in the whole YouTube. Without visiting them, users simply would not

know e.g. how to react to a punishment that might cause their account to be deleted permanently.

1.2. Erasure

Erasure concerns platforms practice of deleting – or at least stopping the public access to – the previous versions of their policies. During our research, we found out that erasure appears to be the rule: no platform we analysed offered a proper archive of their policies. By proper archive, we mean an accessible and searchable repository of all previous versions of all policies. In fact, of the five platforms commented on here, only SoundCloud kept some form of full record of these versions. It can hardly be considered an archive, however. The platform allows its past policies to be accessed through a hyperlink at the bottom of their current Terms of Service, Privacy Policy and Community Guidelines. In this way, by retroactively clicking on a series of links, the user can get access to all previous versions of the policy, and produce her own manual archive, if she wishes. However, even SoundCloud did not record previous versions of non-traditional policy-like documents, such as Help

pages. With the exception of Facebook’s Community Guidelines (see next section), the other four platforms (Twitter, Facebook, YouTube and Instagram) inform only the date of the last version of those three types of policies – without however providing access to the version itself. Similarly to SoundCloud, no information about changes to their Help pages is offered.

As Section 2 mentions, it remains possible to recover many of these previous versions using the WayBack Machine (WBM). However, documents that do not refer to those three main types of policy (Terms of Service, Privacy Agreement and Community Guidelines), such as Help Pages, are much less often archived by the WBM. As a consequence, a hard-to-calculate number of previous versions of platforms policy documents are permanently deleted from the public view. This is not to say of course that all evidence of these versions is lost – platforms certainly hold a copy of each one of them. Erasure is thus less the practice of destroying these archives than of making them permanently private.

1.3. Flaws

While archives of the previous versions of policies are rare, the few which exist are often flawed in multiple ways. One important example is the Community Guidelines of Facebook. Since April 2018, the page of this policy (named by the platform “Community Standards”) also compiles all changes made to the policy. This changelog presents some commendable features, such as its search engine,

its clearly defined topical sections and the use of visuals to indicate what was deleted (in red) and included (in green).

Nonetheless, this is hardly a satisfactory or a complete archive – and not only because it has no record of changes made prior to 2018. The perhaps most important flaw is that, in recording particular changes, and not entire versions, the page makes itself quite hard to be read as a historical archive. If the user wants to know e.g. how the Community Guidelines looked like at a certain point in time, she must retrospectively construct her own version by manually adding and subtracting excerpts from the most recent version.

When doing this, we noted several issues. Per Facebook’s records, the first change to a section titled “Cruel and Insensitive [content]” occurred in July 2019. However, merely subtracting the new content added in that month left the text of the section truncated, as if other changes were not properly recorded. Another inconsistency occurred in a section on “Sexual Solicitation”. According to Facebook’s records, one of the paragraphs of the section was first added in October 2018. However, the same paragraph appears in December 2018 again as “new” (i.e., in green). In the same section, the exact wording of a sentence is described in a Facebook’s footnote as having been changed in December 2018. Yet, in Facebook’s records, the deleted words are not marked as such, i.e. in red and stroke through. Another issue relates to how shifts in the very structure of the document are recorded. From April 2018 to November 2019, the sections “Promoting and Publicizing Crime” and “Coordinating Harm” appeared to exist separately. Then, in November 2019, Facebook merged them. Yet, when we consulted the Community Standards archive, it had no records of what exactly these two sections contained between April 2018 and November 2019.

There are other issues with Facebook’s policies beyond the way their Community Standards page is organized. By the end of 2020, Facebook listed 13 “terms and policies”. Yet these are still not all the policies that could apply to their users. For instance, there was no mention to the “Rights Manager Terms”, the policies that apply to users who also take participate in Facebook’s copyright monetization program – named Rights Manager.

In the case of Twitter, we found out that some of the dates the platform gave to indicate previous versions of their Terms of Service previous versions do not appear to be accurate. In our attempt to

use WBM to create an archive of all versions of this policy, we discovered that there were at least two changes to the text that imported in actual changes to the platform’s rules which were not seemingly recorded as such. On 6 of August,

2008, the company added a full sentence to its Terms of Service: “We reserve the right to reclaim usernames on behalf of businesses or individuals that hold legal claim or trademark on those usernames“. Yet, the date is not recorded as a day in which a new version was released. The same applies to the addition of a shorter sentence (“in accordance with any applicable laws”) on 29 of April, 2009.

2. Conclusion: The Platform Governance Archive

The issues we commented on in the first section are serious. In making their current and previous policies hard or impossible to find, platforms are not only preventing users from understanding the rules that govern(ed) their relationship with companies – they are also concealing from society as whole key evidences of their transformation into central global institutions. For platforms policies also play a performative role, constituting a form of public speech whereby platforms describe how they want to be perceived – their organizational identity, so to speak. In so doing, these documents allow external observers to reflect on how this performance has changed, and why. That is to say, if we want to study the history of these organizations, we must examine how their policies evolved.

With that in mind, we have created a website that aims to archive all versions of all policies of some key social media platforms. The beta version of the Platform Governance Archive (or PGA) is already live at <https://pga.hiig.de>. It contains, mainly, the outcome of months of work manually collecting previous policies versions. This process used both platforms websites and the versions recorded by WBM. To identify “new” versions of a policy, we looked for changes in the policy text that implied in actual changes to the rules of the platform (see the example mentioned above regarding Twitter).

The next step involves automating the process as much as possible, with the use of WBM’s API. This method will hopefully allow us to archive the policies’ history of many other platforms, and not only of “mainstream” ones. Another goal of the Platform Governance Archive is to offer to visitors a way of easily understanding the transformation of these documents – thus, there is the need to use visualization tools. Regardless of any technical advancement, the PGA will remain dependent on WBM’s records, which are hugely incomplete, unfortunately. There are further challenges. Since 2018, for instance, Facebook’s Community Guidelines started being configured in a way that essentially prevents the WBM from recording copies of it. In this case, we have no option but trust in what the platform’s website says.

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